

On Induction Period and After-effect in Photochemical Reactions.

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It is a well known fact that certain chemical reactions show a well defined period of induction, during which the velocity of the reaction increases up to a maximum. This is then followed by the unusual curve of diminishing velocity characteristic of chemical reactions in general. This period of gradually increasing velocity is known as the period of induction. In some markedly photochemical reactions the same phenomenon has been observed. In dark reactions the induction period may be due to the presence of consecutive reactions, catalysing agents or some sort of passive resistance.

The induction period has already been noted in certain photochemical reactions. The bromination of cinnamic acid and stilbene (Ghosh and Purkayastha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 261; 1927, 4, 409; 1927, 4, 553) shows a marked induction period and after-effect. In the oxidation of tartaric acid by bromine an induction period was observed in light by Bunsen and Roscoe (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1857, 100, 513; *Phil. Trans.*, 1857, 147, 355, 601) and by Ghosh and Mukherjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 165.) and in the dark by Sanyal and Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 139, 161). A mixture of benzaldehyde and acetic acid exposed to the light of an electric arc also shows the same phenomenon (Jorisen and Ringer, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1905, 76, 1, 187; *Chem. Weekblad*, 2, 19). Some reactions were carried out with a view to find out whether the induction period and after-effect are due to the formation of intermediate complex or some other cause.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The Bromination of Cinnamic Acid and Stilbene.

These reactions were investigated with the help of a spectro-photometer and the experimental arrangement was the same as before. It has been already noted (Ghosh and Purkayastha, *loc. cit.*) that after the period of induction and after-effect are over, the reaction

systems on exposure to light again pass through a short period of induction.

The influence of the concentration of the acceptors and also of bromine on the period of induction could not be studied accurately on account of the great reactivity of the substances. The results obtained, however, indicate that as the concentration of bromine increases the period of induction also increases, the velocity of the reaction is, of course, independent of the concentration of bromine. The concentration of the acceptor has no effect on the induction period when the concentration is not very small. The influence of the wave-length of light will be apparent from the previous papers. In blue light where the reactions are very rapid the induction period is quite marked but of a shorter duration while in the yellow the velocity is very small and the induction period is very slight. In carbon disulphide no induction period has been observed in yellow light, but in carbon tetrachloride a slight but rather prolonged period of induction has been observed. The following table will give an idea as to the influence of solvents, the acceptors, the intensity of incident radiation and temperature on the induction period.

TABLE I.

Green light (filters as recommended by Plotnikow).

Solvent.	Acceptor.	Conc. of bromine.	Temp.	Intensity.	Induction period in minutes.
CCl ₄	Cinnamic acid	·0282M	30°C	1 Hefner	14 to 15
	"	"	40°C	"	5 to 6
	"	·0197 "	30°C	"	10 to 12
	"	·0197 "	"	·15	17
	Stilbene	·0197 "	"	1	17 to 18
CS ₂	Cinnamic acid	·0197 "	"	·15	7 to 8
	"	·0197 "	"	1	4 to 5
	"	·0197 "	40°C	·15	3 to 4
	Stilbene	·0197 "	30°C	·15	10 to 12

It will be seen from Table I that so far as the effect of these solvents, acceptors, intensity of light and temperature are concerned, anything that increases the velocity causes a diminution in

the period of induction. The velocity of the reaction between stilbene and bromine is less than that of the bromination of cinnamic acid in both the solvents and in all the wave-lengths, but it has a longer period of induction.

Oxidation of Tartaric Acid by Bromine.

This reaction was followed by titration with sodium thiosulphate. The reaction mixtures were placed at the definite distance from a 500 c. p. Pointolite lamp in stoppered bottles. Fig. I shows that

Fig. I.

the induction period increases with increase in the concentration of tartaric acid. This suggests that the phenomenon may be due to the presence of some sort of impurities or negative catalyst in the acid. Fig. II shows that as the concentration of bromine is gradually increased the induction period increases, reaches a maximum and then again diminishes. An explanation of this behaviour is attempted at a later portion of the paper.

Fig. I gives the results of three experiments in which the concentration of bromine was the same (0.048 N) and the concentration of tartaric acid was N, 2N, and 3N respectively. The influence of the concentration of bromine on the period of induction has been

plotted in Fig. II. The concentration of tartaric acid was 1.55N in all the experiments and the concentration of bromine varied from 0.06N to 0.0092N.

It is evident from the curves in Fig. II that the induction period with 0.0092N bromine solution is 40 minutes which gradually increases to 125 minutes for 0.0306N bromine and again falls to 85 minutes for 0.06N bromine.

Fig. II.

Oxidation of Mandelic Acid and β -Phenyl- α -Lactic Acid by Bromine.

β -Phenyl- α -lactic acid reacts with bromine in the dark and the reaction is markedly accelerated by light. The reaction between mandelic acid and bromine is a very slow process but it is strongly accelerated by light. The kinetics of both the reactions and their acceleration by light have been studied and will be shortly published. The reaction shows a period of induction when exposed to light and also an after-effect when the source of illumination is withdrawn. The results are given in Tables II and III. The dark reactions are complicated processes. As the rate of disappearance of bromine is strongly influenced by the formation of hydrobromic acid formed in course of the progress of the reactions, the time at which the initial bromine concentration has fallen to the same value in both the light and dark reactions, has been taken for comparison.

INDUCTION PERIOD

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TABLE II.

Temperature 25°C. Dark reaction.
 Conc. of β -phenyl- α -lactic acid = .11 N.
 Conc. of bromine = .012 N.

Time in minutes.	Conc. of Br ₂ (In dark).	K ₁ (monomolecular).
0	13.0	—
20	9.9	—
50	7.8	Initial
70	6.8	.00685
100	5.7	.00625

Exposed to light.

0	13.5	} Induction period.	
4	12.6		
8	10.75		
11	8.95		

Light cut off.

31	7.25	} After-effect.	.0105
61	5.85		.0085

TABLE III.

Temperature 25°C.
 Conc. of mandelic acid = .125 N. Conc. of bromine = .01215 N.

Time in minutes.	($a-x$).	K ₁ (monomolecular).
0	14.3	—
4	14.15	} Period of induction.
8	13.0	
12	10.15	—
15	8.95	Initial.

Light cut off.

65	7.5	} After-effect.	.000614
125	7.0		.00065

A portion of the same solution was kept in the dark and after about 10 hours the titre of the same volume of solution was found to be 7.65 c.c. of the same thiosulphate solution. The monomolecular constants were calculated by taking this as the zero reading.

Time in minutes.	($a-x$).	K_1 unimolecular.
0	7.65	—
60	7.15	.000502
120	6.7	.000480

The after-effect observed in the above case is small. The reaction has also a fairly high temperature coefficient and slight temperature differences may also account for the small after-effect.

The Influence of Potassium Bromide on Induction Period.

It has been found that if potassium bromide is added to the reaction mixtures before exposure to light the induction period completely disappears or considerably reduced. Of course the bromide concentration should be 8 to 10 times greater than that of bromine. If the bromide concentration is small the induction period is observed but it is considerably less. Even in darkness potassium bromide diminishes the induction period appreciably. The results are given in Tables IV, V, VI, VII and VIII.

TABLE IV.

Conc. of tartaric acid = .375 N.
 Conc. of bromine = .0318 N.
 Temperature 55°C. Dark reaction.

Time in minutes.	($a-x$).	K_1 (monomolecular).
0	34.0	} Induction period.
85	27.1	
110	14.3	—
130	9.0	0.105
141	6.85	.0103
150	5.40	.0106
160	4.0	.0110

TABLE V.

Conc. of tartaric acid = '375 N.
 Conc. of bromine = '016 N. Conc. of KBr = '096 N.
 Temp. 55°C. Dark reaction.

Time in minutes.	($a-x$).	K (monomolecular).
0	17.8	—
35	16.15	'00121
60	14.91	'00129
85	14.0	'00128
115	12.7	'00127
156	11.15	'00130
190	10.0	'00132
240	8.5	'00134

TABLE VI.

Conc. of tartaric Acid = '23 M.
 Conc. of KBr = '048 M.
 Conc. of Br₂ = '0115 M.
 Blue light. Temperature 30°.

Time in minutes.	0	25	70	108	145	190
($a-x$)	14.4	13.6	12.05	10.7	9.25	7.8
x/t	—	'0320	'0336	'0342	'0355	'0347

TABLE VII.

Conc. of mandelic acid = '308 M.
 Conc. of KBr = '096 M.
 Conc. of Br₂ = '0175 M.
 Temp. 30°. Blue light.

Time in minutes.	0	15	30	50	65	85	105	125
($a-x$)	22.6	20.75	11.7	16.5	14.5	12.05	9.8	7.35
k/t	—	'123	'130	'123	'125	'124	'122	'121

TABLE VIII.

Conc. of mandelic acid	=	·308 M.	Temp. 30°C.
Conc. of bromine	=	·023 M.	Blue light.
Time in minutes.	(a-x),		K_1
0	30·2	} Induction period.	
10	28·0		
25	25·1		
38	20·4		
45	16·4		·0135
52	13·0		·0140
59	10·6		·0135
71	7·4		·0133

The experimental facts may be summarised as follows :—

(1) Oxidation of tartaric acid by bromine shows a quite marked induction period both in darkness and also in light.

(2) Oxidation of mandelic acid and β -phenyl- α -lactic acid by bromine shows absolutely no induction period in darkness but it is only manifested on exposure to light.

(3) Potassium bromide diminishes and in some cases causes the complete disappearance of induction period.

(4) Bromination of cinnamic acid and stilbene shows an induction period both in light as also in darkness.

(5) In all cases increase of temperature and the intensity and frequency of incident radiation diminishes the induction period.

Ghosh and Basu (this *Journal*, 1928, 5, 361) has put forward a suggestion to explain the induction period observed in the oxidation of tartaric acid by bromine. They suggest that in the initial stage of the reaction the active bromine atoms are used up in destroying a class of substances known as photo-inhibitors which are almost invariably present in reaction systems and consequently the reaction will proceed at a slower rate in the beginning. On this view it is quite easy to understand the influence of the intensity and frequency of incident radiation. The experimental facts, however, show that this view cannot explain the period of gradually increasing velocity observed in a number of oxidation reactions by bromine.

The existence of the period of induction only in light go to show that in dilute aqueous solutions of bromine probably it is in a hydrated state. It is well known that absorption of moist bromine vapour begins at 6100\AA and for bromine solution it begins somewhat earlier. So it is quite reasonable to assume that in aqueous solution bromine molecules will be mostly in the hydrated state. These hydrated molecules are quite reactive in the dark. The reactivity of free bromine molecules is of course greater. When bromine solution is exposed to light free bromine molecules are produced and probably they are then activated. It is obvious that this will require some time and hence there will be a period of gradually increasing velocity and reaction which proceed quite smoothly in the dark will show this phenomenon when exposed to light. This view may also partly account for the large number of molecules found to be transformed per quantum of energy absorbed in these oxidation reactions.

It has been also found that a dilute solution of alcohol (2 or 3%) and bromine shows a period of gradually increasing velocity when exposed to light. These facts suggest that oxidation reactions by bromine will generally show a period of gradually increasing velocity provided the dark reaction is not very rapid and it is fairly strongly accelerated by light.

In presence of a bromide solution of moderate strength only a small portion of the bromine molecules remains in the hydrated state owing to the reaction $\text{Br}' + \text{Br}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{Br}_3$ and when the concentration of bromide is large in comparison with that of bromine the ratio Br_2/Br_3' may be regarded as constant. The equilibrium constant of the bromide-bromine reaction is .065 (Jakowkin, *Z. physikal Chem.*, 1896, 20, 19). It is easy to see that in a .02 M bromine solution in presence of 2N bromide solution about 65% of bromine molecules will be as Br_3' and in 0.1N bromide the percentage of Br_3' will be about 55. The extinction co-efficient of Br_3' is much greater than that of Br_2 in blue and violet light and there is enough experimental evidence that the activated Br_3' ions do not directly take part in the reaction (results of the author to be communicated shortly). Consequently at such high concentration of Br_3' which has a much greater extinction co-efficient the influence of the hydrated bromine molecules will not be noticeable and the reactions may proceed normally.

At elevated temperatures the induction period considerably diminishes even in absence of any bromide on account of the instability

of the hydrated bromine molecules. On this view the influence of temperature, the intensity and frequency of incident radiation is easily intelligible.

It has been shown that the bromination of cinnamic acid and stilbene and the oxidation of tartaric acid, mandelic acid, and β -phenyl- α -lactic acid shows an after-effect and also a period of gradually increasing velocity. The reaction between hydrogen and chlorine (Taylor's "Physical Chemistry" Vol. II, p. 1220) as has been clearly shown by Weigert and Kellermann shows an after-effect and also an induction period of short duration. No single explanation can possibly account for the existence of the period of induction in all these reactions. The fact that most of the reactions which show an induction period also persist when the source of illumination is withdrawn may lead to the conclusion that the induction period is due to intermediate complex formation.

In the oxidation of tartaric acid by bromine, inhibitors as well as the hydrated state of the bromine molecules are responsible for the existence of this marked induction period and it is more probable that the inhibitors play the more important role. A reference to Fig. II will make it evident that though the concentrations of the bromine solutions are widely different, the reactions proceed normally when practically the same amount of bromine has been used up in all the reaction mixtures. This clearly shows that two side reactions are taking place, namely the normal reaction between bromine and tartaric acid and also the removal of the inhibitor by bromine. The reaction proceeds normally from the instant at which all the inhibitor has been completely oxidised. In the oxidation of mandelic acid and β -phenyl- α -lactic acid, which show no induction period in darkness, the hydrated state of the bromine molecules is alone responsible for the existence of the period of gradually increasing velocity. In hydrogen-chlorine reaction the cause is probably associated with the presence of photo-inhibitors. In the bromination of stilbene and cinnamic acid the induction period is mainly due to the formation of intermediate complexes. The reappearance of the short period of gradually increasing velocity strongly supports this view. The induction period, however, depends also to some extent on the association of bromine molecules with the solvents, and the explanation will be similar to what has been suggested in the case of the oxidation reactions. Extinction coefficient measurements of bromine in different solvents give widely

different values (Plotnikow, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1912, 79, 357), Ghosh and Purkayastha, this *Journal*, 1927, 4, 409) and the natural conclusion is that the bromine molecules are associated with the different solvents.

An explanation may be here put forward for the induction period (Fig. II) observed with bromine solutions of different concentrations in the oxidation of tartaric acid. It has been already noted that in the bromination reactions the induction period increases with increase in the concentration of bromine. So the lower portion of the Curve A in Fig. II is of the same nature. The solubility of bromine in organic solvents is enormously greater than its solubility in water. Even in dilute aqueous solutions, after a certain concentration is reached, there will be appreciable quantities of free bromine molecules and if the concentration is increased beyond this the proportion of free bromine will increase more rapidly and a considerable portion of the reaction will be due to the free bromine molecules. Hence on increasing the bromine concentration beyond this stage the induction period will gradually diminish because of the presence of more and more bromine molecules which have a much greater reactivity.

A fairly large number of reactions is however known which show only an after-effect. The mechanism of the after-effect has not yet been explained. Dhar and Mukherjee (this *Journal*, 1925, 2, 277) investigated a number of reactions exhibiting after-effect and put forward the view that the after-effect might be due to the activation of the inactive molecules by the impact of the activated molecules of the reacting substances. This process will require some-time to die out even after the source of illumination is withdrawn. It should be pointed out here that on proper calculation it will be found that some of the reaction studied by Dhar and Mukherjee do not show any after-effect at all. Calculation of molecular constants should have been made from the instant when the source of illumination is cut off.

It seems more probable that the after-effect is due to the existence of chain reactions and Weigert's suggestion (*Ann. Physik*, 1907, 24, 243) that intermediate complexes or intra-molecular transformation of the light absorbing substances may serve as reaction nuclei in photo-chemical changes is in line with this view. Dhar and Mukherjee think that there is absolutely no experimental fact in favour of intermediate complex formation. It may be said

however, that though there is no direct evidence, some facts indirectly point to the above conclusion. It has been found that in reactions of this type a large number of molecules are transformed per quantum of energy absorbed and consequently the existence of chain reactions or intermediate complex formation may be regarded to be the more probable view.

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